

14 **Abstract**
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16 **Plain Language Summary**
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18 **1 Introduction**

19 The ocean plays a crucial role regulating global carbon cycle in the Earth system
20 absorbing 25-30% of the anthropogenic CO_2 since the beginning of the industrial era (e.g.
21 Le Quéré et al., 2018). The CO_2 emissions from fossil fuels became the dominant source
22 of anthropogenic emissions to the atmosphere from around 1950 (Global Carbon Bud-
23 get 2021; Gruber et al., 2019; Sabine et al., 2004). The exchange and transfer of carbon
24 on relatively short-timescales (from seconds to millennium) are regulated by exchang-
25 ing carbon among the atmosphere, land, and ocean reservoirs through biogeochemical
26 processes (e.g. Ito et al., 2020; Schlesinger and Bernhardt, 2020). Earth System Mod-
27 els (ESMs) are essential tools for understanding the evolution of carbon cycle through
28 simulating a suite of physical and biogeochemical processes in the climate system. The
29 large amount of carbon sink by the ocean plays a crucial role regulating the air borne
30 fraction of CO_2 (Jones et al., 2013; Friedlingstein et al., 2022) and carbon-climate feed-
31 back in the Earth system (Friedlingstein et al., 2006). The accurate representation of
32 ocean carbon cycle and carbon-climate feedback is essential for ESMs to conduct reli-
33 able historical and future projection simulations including the emission-driven type sim-
34 ulations (Jones et al., 2016).

35 Simulating ocean carbon cycle and associated ocean biogeochemical processes are
36 becoming more important assessing marine ecosystems under modern and future climate
37 change, which will directly connect to our understanding of changes in marine resources.
38 This paper introduce the ocean carbon cycle simulations based on the ocean component
39 of the E3SM version 2 (E3SMv2) (Golaz et al., 2022). The ocean component of the E3SMv2
40 is the Model for Prediction Across Scales Ocean (MPAS-O) (Petersen et al., 2019) with
41 the Marine Biogeochemistry Library (MARBL) ((Long et al., 2021)) for an ocean bio-
42 geochemistry model. The MARBL is the ocean biogeochemistry component for the Com-
43 munity Earth System Model, version 2 (CESM2) (Danabasoglu et al., 2020), which in-
44 cludes several new features compared to the predecessor ocean biogeochemistry model,
45 the Biogeochemistry Elemental Cycle (BEC) (Moore et al., 2004) used in E3SMv1 sim-
46 ulations (see Long et al., 2021 for details of new features and Burrows et al., 2020 for
47 the E3SM version 1 (E3SMv1) biogeochemistry simulations (E3SMv1-1-BGC)). One of
48 the main challenge for ocean carbon cycle in E3SMv1-1-BGC simulations were substan-
49 tially weak global ocean carbon uptake (about 1.4 PgC/yr) compared to the other mod-
50 els from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) and recent ob-
51 servations. Moreover, comprehensive evaluations on ocean carbon cycle has not been con-
52 ducted for the E3SMv1-1-BGC simulations. In the E3SMv1 simulations, there are sev-
53 eral ocean physical features missing related to ocean biogeochemical tracer mixing in-
54 cluding the Redi isopycnal mixing (Redi, 1982) and background vertical diffusion. These
55 features have now been incorporated in the E3SMv2 ocean biogeochemistry simulations
56 presented in this study.

57 Based on the new E3SM2 (Golaz et al., 2022), we conducted new ocean biogeochem-
58 istry hindcast simulations forced by the recent atmospheric reanalysis dataset for driv-
59 ing ocean-sea-ice models (E3SMv2G-BGC). The atmospheric reanalysis dataset is from
60 the Japanese 55-year atmospheric reanalysis (JRA-55), referred to JRA55-do (Stewart
61 et al., 2020, Tsujino et al., 2018). The JRA-55do is also used in the CMIP6 endorsed
62 MIP, The Ocean Model Intercomparison Project (OMIP) phase 2 (OMIP2) (e.g. Tsu-

63 jino et al., 2020). The E3SMv2 ocean biogeochemistry hindcast simulations are referred
 64 to as "E3SMv2G-BGC" in this paper. Along with documenting and evaluating the ocean
 65 carbon cycle in E3SMv2G-BGC, the question we would like to address in this study is
 66 to show how changes in ocean background vertical mixing can modulate ocean carbon
 67 uptake in the past decades. The E3SMv2G-BGC follows a similar approach taken in Global
 68 Carbon Budget activities (Friedlingstein et al., 2022) by spinning-up the ocean carbon
 69 cycle model and then conduct an ocean hindcast simulation from 1958-2018. We con-
 70 ducted simulations with and without ocean background vertical diffusion in order to elu-
 71 cidate the sensitivity of ocean carbon uptake to vertical mixing in the model. We be-
 72 gin by showing how the representation global ocean carbon uptake improved compared
 73 to the E3SMv1 simulation, referred to as "E3SMv1-1-BGC" in this study. The E3SMv1-
 74 1-BGC simulation is a coupled-model simulation but the atmospheric carbon dioxide dataset
 75 used for boundary conditions of the simulation is the same as in E3SMv2G-BGC. We
 76 then present climatological ocean biogeochemical features, including dissolved inorganic
 77 carbon (DIC), alkalinity and ventilation tracers (e.g. CFCs) compare against the obser-
 78 vations. At the end of the results, we discuss how imposing background vertical diffu-
 79 sion changes DIC and associated ocean carbon uptake in the past decades by analyzing
 80 two sets of simulations with and without vertical background diffusion. The results pre-
 81 sented here will give a crucial guide for the near future planned coupled carbon cycle sim-
 82 ulations based on the E3SMv2G-BGC. Finally we will introduce how E3SMv2G-BGC
 83 type ocean biogeochemistry simulations could contribute to the community efforts on
 84 the Global Carbon Budget and Regional Carbon Assessment (RECCAP2) using the unique
 85 capability of Regional Refined Mesh simulations (RRMs) (e.g. Brady et al., 2021).

86 2 Methods: Numerical Simulations

87 The ocean biogeochemistry simulations are based on the Model for Prediction Across
 88 Scales-Ocean, the MPAS-Ocean (MPAS-O), an ocean component of the Energy Exas-
 89 cale Earth System Model (E3SM) version 2, E3SMv2 (Golaz et al., 2022). The MPAS-
 90 O is coupled to the Marine Biogeochemistry Library (MARBL) ((Long et al., 2021)) to
 91 simulate ocean carbon and biogeochemical cycles. The MARBL is a prognostic ocean
 92 biogeochemistry model that simulates marine ecosystem dynamics ((Long et al., 2021)).
 93 The model simulates ocean carbon, dissolved oxygen, and nutrients cycles including iron
 94 cycle. The Redi isopycnal mixing is incorporated in the E3SMv2 settings, a global con-
 95 stant value as $400m^2s^{-1}$. Details on model's ocean physics updates are in Golaz et al.,
 96 2022. In addition to the ocean physics updates, we also incorporated a uniform back-
 97 ground vertical diffusion specifically for ocean biogeochemistry simulations to enhance
 98 ocean carbon uptake and thermocline ventilation of dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC).
 99 We choose a global uniform value of $1.5 \times 10^{-5}m^2s^{-1}$ for the background vertical dif-
 100 fusion coefficient.

101 The simulation is based on ocean stand alone configuration forced with atmospheric
 102 reanalysis (refer to as E3SM G-case). The MPAS-O consists of unstructured Centroidal
 103 Voronoi-type meshes (e.g. Ringler et al., 2008) for both the ocean and sea ice compo-
 104 nents of the E3SMv2 (Golaz et al., 2022, in review). The mesh is handled using the JIG-
 105 SAW library (Engwirda, 2017). Here we use the EC30to60E2r2 mesh, the spatial res-
 106 olution approximately range from 30km to 60km depending on latitudes. The simula-
 107 tion is initialized from the ocean physics and biogeochemistry data including the pre-
 108 vious CESM1 model output and the observational dataset (PHC and World Ocean At-
 109 las). Ocean biogeochemistry simulations require a long-term spin-up in general, due to
 110 the equilibration timescales of 1000-5000 years or even more depending on the model (Se-
 111 ferian et al., 2016; Yool et al., 2020) to achieve steady-states including the deep ocean.
 112 Due to limitation in computational resources, we spun-up the model for 100 years be-
 113 fore starting the historical simulation after 1850, when the atmospheric CO_2 starts to

114 increase. We refer this spin-up simulation as ocean a pre-industrial control (piCTL) sim-
 115 ulation (see experimental design in Figure 1).

116 After a model spin-up, we continue the simulation with increasing the atmospheric
 117 CO_2 for 108 years, which corresponds to 1850-1957 (referred as *tranco2* and labeled as
 118 Sim C, see Figure 1). Finally we start the simulation with the interannual atmospheric
 119 forcing and continuous increase in the atmospheric CO_2 applied for 61 years, which cor-
 120 responds to 1958-2018 (we refer to this as a hindcast and labeled as Sim A, see Figure
 121 1 and Table 1). This type of spin-up and transient simulations has been used in the pre-
 122 vious ocean carbon cycle modeling studies (e.g. Lovenduski et al., 2008) and the Global
 123 Carbon Budget project (Friedlingstein et al., 2022). The atmospheric forcing is from the
 124 Japanese reanalysis, JRA-55do to force the ocean model and used in Ocean Model In-
 125 tercomparison Project phase 2 (OMIP2) (Griffies et al., 2016; Orr et al., 2017). More
 126 specifically the climatological atmospheric forcing is from the Repeat Year Forcing 1984-
 127 1985 from the JRA-55do (JRA-RYF8485) and the interannual atmospheric forcing is from
 128 the version 1.4 of JRA-55do (Tsuji no et al., 2018) (JRA55do-IAF). During the spin-up,
 129 we use the pre-industrial value of the atmospheric CO_2 of 284ppm and then start to in-
 130 crease following the observational values after 1850 both following the OMIP-BGC pro-
 131 tocol (Orr et al., 2017). The atmospheric forcing is from the JRA-RYF8485 for piCTL
 132 (100 years) and *tranco2* (1850-1957) and JRA55do-IAF for hindcast (1958-2018) simu-
 133 lations. We apply global sea surface salinity restoring based on monthly climatology sea
 134 surface salinity from PHC climatology with a piston velocity of 50m over 2 months. We
 135 applied the strong sea surface salinity to prevent the Atlantic Meridional Overturning
 136 Circulation (AMOC) to collapse during the simulations. The weak AMOC is one of the
 137 challenge in E3SMv2 (Golaz et al., 2022) but we also note that the atmospheric forcing
 138 from JRA-55do could also contribute to the weakening of AMOC during the model spin-
 139 up and requires some tuning in model simulations (Tsuji no et al., 2020).

140 The ocean physics and biogeochemistry model output is saved in a monthly mean
 141 frequency for all simulations but we mainly focus on analyzing the annual mean model
 142 output in this study. To recall, the horizontal grid is in unstructured mesh (the EC30to60E2r2
 143 mesh) including 60 vertical layers ranging from 10m thick at the surface to 250m thick
 144 in the deep ocean, the same as in the Petersen et al., (2019). The model output has been
 145 re-gridded to 1 degrees horizontal resolutions in order to facilitate the analysis and com-
 146 parison with the observational dataset from World Ocean Atlas 2018, GLODAPv2, and
 147 SeaFlux. The vertical resolution is 33 vertical layers following the previous World Ocean
 148 Atlas 2009 to reduce the size of model output but we also prepared model output keep-
 149 ing the model’s original 60 vertical layers for discussion of vertical carbon transfer in the
 150 latter section (Results XXX). The model output with 1 degrees horizontal resolutions
 151 and 33 vertical layers is mainly used in ocean carbon cycle evaluations. The reduced re-
 152 gridded model output will serve as a community resources to facilitate the ocean bio-
 153 geochemistry studies using E3SMv2G-BGC such as the DOE University projects and will
 154 made it available for public usage (Takano et al., XXX, Data Link).

Table 1. Simulation ID(tag)s and Duration^a

IDs	Duration (years)
<i>bgc1 – piCTL</i>	100
<i>bgc1 – tranco2</i>	108 (1850-1957)
<i>bgc1 – hindcast</i>	61 (1958-2018)

^aHindcast corresponds to JRA-55do ver1.4 interannual atmospheric forcing from 1958-2018.

E3SM2 Ocean Biogeochemistry Hindcast Simulation Experimental Design (E3SMv2G-BGC)

Figure 1. Experimental design of the E3SM2 ocean biogeochemistry hindcast simulations. The experimental design is similar to the approach taken in the Global Carbon Budget project. ICs are initial conditions.

3 Methods: Observational Dataset

For the long-term from pre-industrial to modern evaluations of global ocean carbon uptake, we used the reconstructed air-sea CO_2 flux dataset from Khatiwala et al., (2009) (Figure 2, see also Yool et al., 2021 for an example). For more recent evaluations of ocean carbon cycle, we use harmonized air-sea CO_2 flux and surface pCO_2 data products, SeaFlux (Fay et al., 2021). SeaFlux is an ensemble data products, based on six global observation-based mapping products (CMEMS-FFNN, CSIR-ML6, JENA-MLS, JMA-MLR, MPI-SOMFFN, NIES-FNN, see Fay et al., 2021 for details). These products adjust the methodological inconsistencies in flux calculations (Fay et al., 2021). We use ensemble mean of these products for the model and observation comparison. The pre-industrial out-gassing due to river inputs is one of the major uncertainties estimating ocean carbon sink from the observations and need some type of corrections to compare with the model simulations. Here we follow the methods from Hauck et al., (2020) for model and observations comparison and briefly discuss potential uncertainties due to the impact of pre-industrial river input. The regional patterns of pre-industrial out-gassing is still uncertain in observations (with a limited model based estimates from Lacroix et al., 2021 for example), so here we focus mainly on climatological pattern comparison for the global map and zonal mean transects, similar to the evaluation approach in the CESM2 MARBL from Long et al., (2021). The climatological dataset from the observations are from the World Ocean Atlas 2018 and GLODAPv2 (REF), including sea water temperature, potential density, mixed layer depth, dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC), alkalinity, and CFC-11 for ventilation tracers.

4 Results and Discussion

In this section, we present the diagnostics of the simulations, focusing on discussion of ocean carbon cycle.

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4.1 Equilibrium States of the Ocean Simulation

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Model's equilibrium states (steady-states) is an important aspect to check since the model drift could impact on the assessment and evaluations of ocean biogeochemistry (Sferian et al., 2016). Based on the total 269 years of the piCTL simulation (SimB), we examined the model's equilibrium states focusing on ocean carbon cycle. The spin-up is based on the JRA-RYF8485 Repeat Year Forcing (Stewart et. al., 2020) ends up in relatively warm ocean states, global mean sea surface temperature (SST) of 18.1 degC. This is within the range of sea surface temperature from three different simulations based on the same atmospheric forcing presented in Stewart et. al., 2020. Despite the fact that the JRA-RYF8485 is designed to achieve "cold" mean states (Stewart et. al., 2020), the magnitude of global mean SST is higher than that of the coupled simulation from the E3SM-1-1B due to inclusion of post-industrial signal in the atmospheric forcing. We also note that physical state remains the same after the spin-up (year 100, corresponds to year after the 1850) since we continue using the same atmospheric forcing from year 100 (1850) to 208 (1958) despite increasing the atmospheric CO_2 in the transient CO_2 simulation (tranco2).

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The ocean control simulation has been extended up to year 269 (i.e. 2018), which covers the whole simulation period (Figure 1). This enables us to quantify model's drift potentially included in the historical simulations (Sim A) when evaluating ocean carbon cycle. The global net air-sea CO_2 flux (i.e. ocean carbon sink) from the full simulations show long-term transition of increasing ocean carbon uptake from the pre-industrial to the recent period (Figure 2). The global net air-sea CO_2 flux reach quasi-steady states towards towards the end of the simulation particularly within the last 61 years, corresponds to the hindcast period from 1958-2018. The air-sea CO_2 flux has an off-set in the piCTL simulation approximately 0.3 PgC/yr (positive is the uptake of carbon into the ocean). Despite the off-set of steady-states ocean carbon uptake, the ocean carbon cycle simulation from E3SMv2G-BGC shows substantial improvements in historical ocean carbon uptake compared to the predecessor E3SMv1-1-BGC simulation (Figure 2). We will discuss more on historical ocean carbon cycle in the simulations in the next section.

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Supplementary Figure for Model's Equilibrium States

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The sea surface temperature is reaching steady-state towards a global mean value of 18.1 degC after about 100 years, higher than the pre-industrial value due to atmospheric forcing used in this simulation and similar to what is shown in Stewart et al., (2020). The biological variables, global sum of primary production takes slightly longer to equilibrate in total about 200 years. The global primary production is about 40 PgC/yr and export production is 5.6 PgC/yr. The export production is higher and improved compared to the E3SM-1-1B simulation but still in a low range of values compared to other CMIP models. Overall, the ocean control simulation shows that the upper ocean carbon cycle related variables are quasi-equilibrated by the time of the ocean hindcast simulation (after year 208, corresponds to 1958).

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Note: Check and correct the unit of primary and export production. primary production, depth integration is missing in this rough calculations and unit is not correct for export production in the output, cm-1 factor.

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4.2 Global Ocean Carbon Uptake and Historical Transition

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We show the timeseries of the net global air-sea CO_2 flux, a common metric quantifying ocean carbon uptake, from the simulations along with the observational derived estimate of Khatiwala et al., (2009). Here we compare the E3SM2G ocean biogeochemistry simulation with the predecessor E3SMv1-1-BGC, a coupled model simulation presented in Burrows et al., (2020) since no ocean biogeochemistry stand-alone simulation has been conducted with E3SMv1. Despite the differences between the coupled and ocean stand-

Figure 2. Global sum of air-sea CO_2 flux from a suite of E3SMv2G-BGC simulations and the E3SMv1.1-BGC simulation from Burrows et al., (2020). The observational estimate is in gray shading based on a historical reconstruction from Khatiwala et al., (2009).

230 alone simulations, the external forcing from the raise in atmospheric CO_2 is common among
 231 the simulations and the anthropogenic carbon uptake are likely to be similar. The simu-
 232 lations from E3SMv2G-BGC contains piCTL to hindcast simulations (Figure 1, piCTL
 233 tranco2 - hindcast). To re-call within the 100 years of spin-up, the model equilibrates
 234 to overall 0.2-0.3 PgC/yr uptake in the piCTL simulations. The overall drift is small com-
 235 pared to the anthropogenic ocean carbon uptake after 1850s (Figure 2).

236 Despite the differences in atmospheric forcing among the simulations, the E3SMv2G-
 237 BGC ocean biogeochemistry simulations overall show an improvement in global ocean
 238 carbon uptake compared to the E3SMv1.1-BGC (Figure 1, the blue line). The air-sea
 239 CO_2 flux shows growth from the 1850s until the 1930s, followed by slow down of the growth
 240 until the 1950s and strong continuous growth to the present day (Yool et al., 2021). The
 241 E3SMv1.1-BGC shows substantially weak global ocean carbon uptake, particularly the
 242 strong growth after 1950s were lacking ending up in about less than 1.5 PgC/yr. The
 243 strengthening in global ocean carbon uptake in E3SM2G is likely due to enhanced ver-
 244 tical mixing of carbon in broad regions. More regionally specific results and discussion
 245 are in the latter section (Result section XXX). The inclusion of vertical background dif-
 246 fusion and possibly the Redi isopycnal mixing, which was absent in E3SMv1.1-BGC sup-
 247 ports the thermocline ventilation and mixing broad regions, which could results in en-
 248 hanced air-sea CO_2 flux into the ocean.

249 4.3 Climatological Distributions of Ocean Carbon Sink

250 The climartological distributions of air-sea CO_2 flux from the E3SMv2G-BGC over-
 251 all simulate the observed distributions, strong de-gassing in the tropical Pacific ocean
 252 and ocean carbon uptake in mid to high latitudes regions. The de-gassing region in the
 253 central tropical Pacific ocean has been suppressed in the E3SM2G compared to the E3SMv1-
 254 1-BGC simulation, more closer to the observations. The ocean carbon uptake in the North-

ern western boundary current regions is much stronger compared to the observations. Despite strong ocean carbon uptake in the Northern western boundary current regions, the amount of uptake has been slightly increased in E3SM2G compared to E3SM-1-1B, possibly the role of Redi isopycnal mixing and background vertical diffusion included in E3SM2G.

The globally integrated climatological air-sea CO_2 flux, as shown in white numbers in upper left of each panel in Figure 3, from the E3SM2G is 1.87 PgC/yr, approximately 0.6 PgC/yr larger than the E3SM-1-1B. This indicates that global ocean carbon sink is stronger in the E3SM2G simulation compared to the predecessor*. The E3SMv2G-BGC simulated air-sea CO_2 flux is larger in magnitude than the observational product (1.35 PgC/yr). The discrepancy is not significant if riverine carbon inputs are properly accounted for in the comparison (Long et al., 2021; Friedlingstein et al., 2022). One of the major regions contributing to strengthening in global ocean carbon uptake is the subtropical regions (i.e. boundary between subtropical gyre and subpolar gyre region). This indicates that despite the importance of substantial anthropogenic carbon uptake in the North Atlantic and the Southern Ocean (References), the role of ocean carbon uptake in inter-gyre boundaries is non negligible sustaining the global ocean carbon uptake. This may be one of the source of uncertainties simulating global ocean carbon uptake in the models. The other feature missing in the simulations is the de-gassing in the subpolar North Pacific ocean we see in the observations (Figure 3c). The E3SMv1-1-BGC shows ocean carbon uptake in this region but the magnitudes are suppressed in the E3SMv2G-BGC, which is another improvement in the new simulation.

Figure 3. Climatological distributions of air-sea CO_2 flux from the E3SMv2G-BGC ocean biogeochemistry hindcast simulation, E3SMv1-1-BGC historical simulation, and observations. The Nbk is a simulation with no background vertical diffusion.*

The climatological zonally mean air-sea CO_2 flux exhibit substantial differences in subtropical gyre regions, light gray shaded regions in Figure 4, much stronger ocean carbon uptake in these regions for the E3SMv2G-BGC compared to the E3SMv1-1-BGC.

Figure 4. Climatological difference distributions of air-sea CO_2 flux from the E3SMv2G-BGC ocean biogeochemistry hindcast simulations.

280 Overall ocean carbon uptake in these regions contributes to enhanced global carbon up-
 281 take. Note that the zonal mean air-sea CO_2 from the observational product is not ad-
 282 justed with the pre-industrial river input (i.e. de-gassing) and the magnitudes could be
 283 larger compared to what is shown in Figure 4. Despite the updates in ocean mixing pa-
 284 rameterization in the E3SM2G, the ocean carbon uptake in the high-latitude Southern
 285 Ocean shows similar magnitude to that of E3SMv1-1-BGC. One noticeable differences
 286 is in the mid-latitude ocean carbon uptake, which is substantially stronger than the E3SM-
 287 1-1B. The increase in ocean carbon uptake in the Northern mid-latitude is likely due to
 288 enhanced ocean carbon update in the Gulf Stream regions, as we can see in the clima-
 289 tological air-sea CO_2 flux maps in Figure 3. Note that the ocean carbon uptake in the
 290 high-latitude Southern Ocean is much higher in other CMIP6 models, which likely con-
 291 tributes to higher global ocean carbon uptake.

292 4.4 Climatological Mixed Layer Depth

293 Hereafter we focus on E3SMv2G-BGC evaluations starting from ocean mixed layer
 294 depths (MLD). The ocean mixed layer depths are an important factor controlling the
 295 the upper ocean uptake of carbon and other biogeochemical tracer uptake. The ocean
 296 properties are homogenized within the mixed layer depths and important connecting
 297 as a gateway from the surface water ventilating water masses into the interior ocean (**mixed
 298 layer, water mass and ventilation references**). **Notably, the mixed layer depth in the model
 299 manifests as a result of interactions between the vertical mixing scheme (Large et al.,
 300 1994) and both parameterized (e.g., Danabasoglu et al., 2010; Fox-Kemper et al., 2008;
 301 Gent and McWilliams, 1990) and resolved transport controlling stratification (Small et
 302 al., 2020).**

303 The simulated Northern hemisphere winter (January-February-March) and sum-
 304 mer (July-August-September) mixed layer depth (based on density criteria) shows over-
 305 all similar broad patterns compared to the observational based mixed layer depth but
 306 there are several noticeable biases. In the Northern hemisphere in winter, the mixed layer
 307 depth in the western boundary current regions are substantially deeper compared to the
 308 observations (about 150m), which could be linked to overestimates in ocean carbon up-
 309 take. The deep bias in the mixed layer depth is also evident in the Southern Ocean in
 310 the winter season in the Southern hemisphere. However, the deeper mixed layer in the
 311 Southern Ocean does not necessary lead to enhanced uptake in the high-latitudes South-
 312 ern Ocean (similar in both E3SMv1-1-BGC and E3SMv2G-BGC and lower compared
 313 to CESM2). Why is this? Already oversaturated in this region, carbonate chemistry rea-
 314 son, biology is substantially weak for some reason, or Taka's air-sea disequilibrium ar-
 315 gument?

Figure 5. Climatological zonal mean distributions of air-sea CO_2 flux from the E3SMv2G-BGC ocean biogeochemistry hindcast simulation, E3SMv1.1-BGC historical simulation, and observations.*

316 In E3SM2, the bias in the Southern Ocean mixed layer depth can also be an off-
 317 set in the latitudinal position of the deepest MLD in the model compared to the data
 318 as mentioned in Pertsersen et al., (2019). The overall shallow bias in mixed layer depth
 319 in the Southern summer subtropical to mid-latitudes is also consistent with the previous
 320 simulations.

321 4.5 Ocean Carbon Cycle Evaluations: Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC) 322 and Alkalinity

323 The ocean transects of chemical tracers show vertical distributions of tracers and
 324 inference on ventilation of ocean carbon (Figure 7, 8 ...). The E3SMv2G-BGC captures
 325 broad distributions of DIC but there are noticeable differences in the high-latitudes At-
 326 lantic and sub-tropical regions, where we see lower DIC compared to the CESM2 and
 327 GLODAPv2. Upper ocean transects plot high-light the low DIC pools in between 20-
 328 40 degrees bands in upper couple hundred meters depth. Despited the inclusion of back-
 329 ground vertical mixing in E3SMv2, the mixing and homogenization (or transport) of DIC,
 330 which is the thermocline carbon ventilation could be still weak compared to the CESM2
 331 and GLODAPv2. This low DIC features are commomn among the Atlantic and Pacific
 332 Oceans. The DIC distributions in the tropical interior ocean shows lower DIC compared
 333 to CESM2 and closer to observations, indicating the trapping of carbon in this region
 334 might be lower in E3SM2. The other noticable feature is the deep DIC upwelling in the
 335 high latitudes Southern Ocean. No deep Pacific trapping of high DIC in CESM2 (ev-
 336 ident in a coupled model simulation) or E3SMv2G-BGC.

Figure 6. Climatological Northern hemisphere summer (JJA) and winter (DJF) distributions of mixed layer depth (MLD) from the E3SMv2G-BGC ocean biogeochemistry hindcast simulation, and observations from Holte et al., (2017).*

Figure 7. Climatological distribution of surface salinity normalized DIC and alkalinity (sDIC and sAlk) from the E3SMv2G-BGC ocean biogeochemistry hindcast simulation, and observations from GLODAPv2.*

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4.6 Ocean Transects: CFCs Ventilation Tracers

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The ventilation tracers such as CFCs will support us on discussing the ventilation efficiency of tracers in the ocean. Similar to CESM2, the passive tracers are simulated the MPAS-O framework (not within MARBL as mentioned in Long et al., (2021)). CFCs tracks ventilation within several decades (e.g., Dutay et al., 2002), which is more use-

Figure 8. Climatological zonal transects of (salinity normalized) dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) from the E3SMv2G-BGC ocean biogeochemistry hindcast simulation, and observations from GLODAPv2* from the global ocean.

342 full for assessing ventilation and mixing in the thermocline (prepare CFC bias plot and
 343 upper 1000m plot focusing on thermocline). E3SMv2G-BGC is still lacking (deficit) in
 344 thermocline ventilation, which is obvious by comparing with CESM2 and GLODAPv2
 345 (Figure XXX). The penetration of CFC-11 in the Northern high latitude (around 60N),
 346 which indicates that convective mixing could be weak in E3SMv2G-BGC and CESM2
 347 compared to the GLODAPv2 (or NADW formation is weak). The subtropical thermo-
 348 cline CFC-11 still low in E3SMv2G-BGC confined to upper few hundred meters com-
 349 pared to more deeper penetration particular in the southern subtropical ocean in CESM2
 350 and GLODAPv2.

351 We need to cite reference referring to thermocline ventilation and ocean carbon up-
 352 take in the ocean to extend discussion. Cite Iudicone’s paper and expand discussion here.

353 4.7 Regional Ocean Carbon Sink

354 Following the framework of the global carbon budget analysis, we separate the global
 355 ocean into three latitudinal bands in this analysis, the northern band ($> 30N$), the tropi-
 356 cal sub-tropical band ($< 30N, > 30S$), and the southern band ($< 30S$) (Figure XX).
 357 The observational estimates (product) is adjusted with pre-industrial river input flux fol-
 358 lowing Hauck et al., (2020). The northern band shows gradual increase in ocean carbon
 359 uptake, which is consistent among simulations and observations except E3SMv1-1-BGC
 360 drops towards the end of the simulation.

Overall the Northern latitudes takes up about 1.0 PgC/yr towards the end of 2020s, which is consistent among the models and observations. The most striking difference between the predecessor model, E3SMv1-1-BGC and the new E3SMv2G-BGC is the ocean carbon uptake in the sub-tropics and tropical oceans. The two model simulations show very close trajectory and magnitudes of ocean carbon uptake, which is somewhat higher than the observations (gray line). As we pointed out in the previous section, the ocean carbon uptake (climatology) in this band (region) was substantially weak in the E3SMv1-1-BGC, which ends up pushing the total global carbon uptake down. This has been much improved, likely due to enhanced carbon mixing and ventilation in the subtropical thermocline. The southern ocean (southern bands) carbon uptake is overall underestimated compared to the observations, which gives global lower bias in the model simulations. We note that the observational data gaps in the Southern Ocean brings us huge uncertainties and need to be interpreted in caution. Despite the lower ocean carbon uptake in the simulations, the decadal carbon uptake in E3SMv1-1-BGC and E3SMv2G-BGC are both even more lower compared to CESM2, which indicates that the Southern Ocean carbon uptake could possibly be substantially weak in this model (despite the deep mixed layer depth in winter).

4.8 Timescale separations: Linear Trend of Ocean Carbon Uptake

Over the historical period (1958-2018), most of the regions shows ocean carbon uptake (i.e. positive trend in air-sea CO_2 flux in Figure XXX) including the subtropical, mid-latitude regions and the Southern Ocean. Strong out-gassing features are evident in the central tropical Pacific Ocean. The other spots showing negative trend is polar North Atlantic and coastal regions off Peru/Chile in the Pacific Ocean. Both Kuroshio and Gulf Stream (the Northern western boundary current regions) show as hotspots in ocean carbon uptake) with more zonally elongated features in the Kuroshio, North Pacific region.

(check CESM2 and zonal linear trend, standard deviation).

4.9 Summary and Discussion

The E3SM2G showed improvements in global ocean carbon sink in the historical period compared to E3SMv1-1-BGC. The primary reason for the increase in ocean carbon uptake is the role of subtropical oceans in both hemisphere as shown in climatological distributions and temporal evolution of air-sea CO_2 flux in this region. The main difference between the two simulations are the physical process tuning, parameterization in the model, the Redi isopycnal mixing and background vertical diffusion imposed. It is likely that the background vertical diffusion intensified the thermocline DIC (carbon) mixing in this region, changed the entrainment and ends up uptaking more carbon into the ocean. This was absent in the E3SM1-1B because of lack of mixing in this depth.

Comparison between the DIC distributions and changes in the boundary layer depth and mixed layer depth also give us some clue on this. The results highlight the importance of thermocline DIC (carbon) mixing controlling the global ocean carbon uptake and needs to be further evaluated among the models for improved ocean carbon uptake in the simulations. Mixed layer bias could also lead to different entrainment rate of DIC (carbon) into the upper ocean, which could impact on ocean carbon uptake. Further development and implementation of physical mixing parameterization could further lead to improvements in air-sea gas exchange processes and transport of tracers in the interior ocean.

(check KPP mixing scheme, boundary layer vs mixed layer).

408 **5 Open Research**

409 AGU requires an Availability Statement for the underlying data needed to under-
410 stand, evaluate, and build upon the reported research at the time of peer review and pub-
411 lication.

412 Data availability including the E3SM2 hindcast simulations and observational dataset.

413 Dataset and codes to reproduce the results...

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